

CONSTRAINTS FACED AND SUGGESTIONS MADE BY THE POMEGRANATE CULTIVATORS IN ADOPTION OF IMPROVED POMEGRANATE CULTIVATION PRACTICES

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Abstract

This study was conducted in Aurangabad district of Maharashtra state with a view to know Constraints faced and suggestions made by the pomegranate cultivators in adoption of improved pomegranate cultivation practices during the year 2021-22. From the district, four talukas were selected purposively where pomegranate is extensively cultivated. Among four talukas of Aurangabad district, Three villages from each tahsil were selected, a total number of 12 villages were selected from the four tahsil. The data from the pomegranate cultivators were collected through personal interview schedule. An Ex-post-facto research design was followed for the study. The collected data was analyzed, classified and tabulated. Statistical tools such as frequency and percentage were used to interpret findings and draw conclusions. With concern to chemical fertilizers majority of pomegranate cultivators were having constraints faced about liquid fertilizers seems expensive. In the context of weed management majority of pomegranate cultivators were facing the problems of lack of knowledge about usage of weedicides in scientific way. Majority (79.17%) of the pomegranate cultivators suggested get information and training of the harvesting of the fruit.

Key word: Constraints, Suggestions, Improved cultivation practices, Pomegranate.

Introduction

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is an important fruit of tropical and subtropical regions of World. It commonly known as Anar, Dalib, Matulum. The centre of origin of pomegranate is Iran where it was first cultivated in 2000 B.C. It is extensively cultivated in various countries which includes Spain, Morocco, Egypt, Iran, China, Japan, USA, Russia, Pakistan, India and other Mediterranean countries. Pomegranate occupies 18th placed based on production among the world's main fruit crops.

India is world's largest producer of pomegranates and it produces finest quality pomegranate throughout the year. The total area under pomegranate crop in India 2018-19 is approximately 2.46 lack hectare and production is 28.65 lack metric tons. During the year 2018-19, 67.89 thousand MT fruits exported from India and it worth Rs. 6885 million, which shows that there is tremendous potential in fruit export (Anonymous, 2019). UAE, Nepal, Saudi Arab, Oman, Qatar, Netherland, Kuwait, Baharin, Srilanka, Egypt, Vietnam, Singapore are the major destinations were pomegranates exported from India.

Maharashtra contributes 64.43% in total production of pomegranates from India and it ranks first in total production followed by Karnataka, Gujrat, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh etc. It is an important fruit crop of Maharashtra and it is cultivated in 43,151 ha. Area with total production of 4,31,510 tones. In Maharashtra, production is mainly concentrated in the Western Maharashtra region and the Marathwada region. Commercial cultivation of pomegranate takes place in Solapur, Nashik, Ahmednagar, Pune, Dhule, Aurangabad, Satara, Osmanabad and Latur districts of Maharashtra. The varieties like Bhagwa, Super Bhagwa, Arakta, Ganesh, Mrudula, Dholka popularly grown in Maharashtra.

In Marathwada, pomegranate is commercially cultivated in Aurangabad, Beed, Jalna, Osmanabad and Latur districts. Jalna and Aurangabad are the major pomegranate growing districts in which area under pomegranate cultivation in jalna is 2,424 ha and overall production is about 19,100 tonnes. While area under pomegranate cultivation in Aurangabad is 7,300 ha and production is 31,800 tonnes. (Anonymous, 2018).

Bhagawa the variety of pomegranate growing in major districts of Marathwada. The fruit is glossy red in colour with soft seeds and high T.S.S. Variety Ganesh is also grown having yellow to reddish yellow rind colour, having light pink arils and soft seeds. Fruit weights between 225-250 gms with medium T.S.S Agricultural scientist 'Dr Cheema' did the pioneering work in 1944 at Ganeshkhind, Pune selecting elite plants collected from Alandi and Dholka, cross breed of which gave rise to GBI-1, latter on renamed as 'Ganesh' as a chance seedling

Pomegranate contains calcium, phosphorous, iron and other mineral as well as 'B' and 'C' vitamins. It prefers for its cool, refreshing juice and also for its different medicinal properties. Bark and rind of fruit are commonly used in the therapeutics in dysentery and diarrhea. Juice is used as medicine for leprosy.

However it is observed that many pomegranate cultivators faces some constraints during pomegranate cultivation. Hence the study was conducted with following specific objectives include to ascertain the constraints faced and suggestions made by the pomegranate cultivators in adoption of improved pomegranate cultivation practices.

Materials And Methods

The present study was conducted in the Aurangabad district of Marathwada region of Maharashtra state during 2021-2022, mainly because the researcher is the native of state and is well proficient with socio-cultural situation and the local language of that area. This helped in establishing communication with the respondents and obtaining fiducial and authenticate information. The tahsil namely Aurangabad, Paithan, Phulambri, Kannad were selected purposively as pomegranate growers were comparatively more in this area. The villages were selected purposively from Aurangabad, Paithan, Phulambri and Kannad tahsil, where maximum number of pomegranate growers observed. Three villages from each tahsil Thus, a total number of 12 villages were selected from the four tahsil. List of selected villages namely Jadgaon, Hivra and Tongaon were selected from Aurangabad taluka Tupewadi, Balanagar, Kadethan were selected from Paithan taluka Haladgaon khurd, Haladgaon budroog, Wakod from Phulabri taluka and Bahirgaon, Dongaon, Chikalthan from the Kannad district. From each village ten pomegranate growers were selected from the list provided by talathi and Agriculture Assistant of each village. Thus, a total 120 pomegranate farmers were selected as sample respondents for the study. The data were gathered through personal interview method with the help structured schedule consisting of various items concern with the objective of study. An Ex-post-facto research design was used for the present study. The collected data was analysed, classified and tabulated. Statistical tools such as frequency and percentage were used to interpret findings and draw conclusions.

Results And Discussions

Constraints faced and suggestions made by the pomegranate cultivators in adoption of improved pomegranate cultivation practices.

Constraints faced by the pomegranate cultivators in adoption of improved pomegranate cultivation practices.

One of the objectives of the study was to find out the constraints faced by the pomegranate cultivators in the adoption of improved

pomegranate cultivation practices. Comprehensive information about constraints faced by pomegranate cultivators under study is delineated in Table 1.

Table 1: Constraints faced by pomegranate cultivators: (N=120)

S.N	Constrains	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
	Land and preparatory tillage			
A	1. The type of soil suitable for pomegranate cultivation is not known.	25	2.83	XIII
	2. Implements are not available for preparatory tillage	45	37.50	X
	3. No pair of bullock is available for ploughing.	30	25.00	XII
	Preparatory tillage of land seems expensive.	75	62.50	VI
	Selection of variety and sowing			
B	1. There is no proper information about the recommended variety	50	41.67	IX
	2. Recommended grafts are not available to the farmers.	85	70.83	IV
	3. Grafts are expensive.	90	75.00	II
	4. There is lack of knowledge of recommended scientific method for plantation.	88	73.33	III
	5. Lack of availability of equipments which are required for cultivation.	45	37.50	X
	Usage of chemical fertilizers			
C	1. The exact amount of chemical fertilizer is not known.	80	66.67	V
	2. The chemical fertilizers are expensive.	90	75.00	II
	3. Liquid ferlizers are expensive.	95	79.17	I
D	Manure and compost fertilizers			
	1. Do not know how to prepare manure in a scientific way.	70	58.33	VII
	2. Due to shortage of the farm animals, it is becoming difficult to make manure.	85	70.83	IV
	3. Quality manure is not available in the market.	75	62.50	VI
	4. It seems expensive to buy manure from market.	70	58.33	VII
E	Weed Management			
	1. There is lack of knowledge about when to control weed.	50	41.67	IX
	2. Lack of knowledge about usage of weedicides in scientific way.	95	79.17	I
	3. Don't know the exact time of weed management.	40	33.33	XI
F	Irrigation method			
	1. Low availability of irrigation water.	30	25.00	XII
	2. There is lack of knowledge which irrigation method is good.	22	18.33	XIV
	3. No proper knowledge about drip irrigation.	20	16.67	XV
	4. Drip irrigation kits are expensive.	85	70.83	IV
	5. The cost of repairing drip irrigation is high.	90	75.00	II
	6. There is no proper subsidy on drip irrigation.	50	41.67	IX
G	Crop protection			
	1. There is no scientific information about pomegranate crop protection.	75	62.50	VI
	2. Necessary crop protection chemicals are not affordable.	70	58.33	VII
	3. Crop protection chemicals are not available at the right time.	55	45.83	VIII
	4. No knowledge of crop pest.	45	37.50	X
H	Other difficulties			
	1. Lack of timely power supply.	85	70.83	IV
	2. The market price is not getting right.	90	75.00	II
	3. The cost of transportation is high.	95	79.17	I
	4. Not getting proper information from the concerned extension department.	55	45.83	VIII
	5. There is a shortage of labour.	80	66.67	V

Table 1 depicts data regarding constraints faced by pomegranate cultivators related to land and preparatory tillage. It is evident from the data that 2.83, 37.50, 25.00, per cent pomegranate cultivators were having problems of suitable soil type not known, inavailability of implements for preparatory tillage, no pair of bullock is available for ploughing, whereas 62.50 per cent of pomegranate cultivators expressed that the preparatory tillage for the pomegranate cultivation seems expensive.

Regarding variety and sowing 41.67, 70.83, 75.00, 73.33 and 37.50 per cent pomegranate cultivators were having problems about lack of proper information about the recommended variety, recommended grafts are not available, grafts are expensive, lack of knowledge of recommended scientific method for plantation and lack of availability of equipments which are required for cultivation respectively. On the basis of chemical fertilizers the constraints faced by pomegranate cultivators were about 66.67, 75.00, 79.17 per cent of the pomegranate cultivators were having problems about the exact

amount of chemical fertilizers to be used is not known, the chemical fertilizers are expensive, and also the liquid fertilizers seems expensive.

In accordance with the manures and compost fertilizers the percentage about 58.33, 70.83, 62.50, and 58.33 per cent of pomegranate cultivators were facing the problem of how to prepare manure in a scientific way, due to shortage of farm animals, it is becoming difficult to make manure and the quality manure is not available in the market and it seems expensive to buy manure from market.

In the context of weed management the percentage of 41.67%, 79.17%, 33.33% of pomegranate cultivators were facing the problems of lack of knowledge about when to control weed, lack of knowledge about usage of weedicides in scientific way and don't know the exact time of weed management respectively.

In the utilization of the irrigation method there the 25.00, 18.33, 16.67, 70.83, 75.00, 41.67 per cent of the pomegranate cultivators were facing the problems of the low availability of the irrigation water, there is lack of knowledge which irrigation method is good, no

proper knowledge about drip irrigation, drip irrigation kits are expensive, the cost of repairing drip irrigation is high, there is no proper subsidy on drip irrigation respectively.

In the context of crop protection the problems faced by pomegranate cultivators are no scientific information about pomegranate crop protection, necessary crop protection chemicals are not affordable, crop protection chemicals are not available at the right time, and no knowledge of crop pest and the percentile followed by those problems are 62.5, 58.33, 45.83, and 37.50 per cent respectively.

There are also some other difficulties like lack of timely power supply, the market price is not getting right, the cost of transportation is high, not getting proper information from the concerned extension department and there is a shortage of labour which shows the percentage of 70.83, 75.00, 79.17, 45.83, 66.67 respectively.

Suggestions made by the pomegranate cultivators in adoption of improved pomegranate cultivation practices.

The data from the Table 2 revealed that, the suggestions made by the farmer to solar energy utilization in farming system better intentioned. These suggestions are discussed as below;

Table 2 : Suggestions made by the pomegranate cultivators in adopting the improved pomegranate cultivation practices

Sr. No.	Suggestions	Pomegranate cultivators		
		Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	The proper technology of pomegranate cultivation is not yet known.	80	66.67	IV
2	The quantity and timing of the fertilizers to be given to the fruit cultivators should be known.	85	70.83	III
3	Get complete knowledge about the bahar method in pomegranate.	90	75.00	II
4	Get proper information about pest and pest management.	70	58.33	VI
5	Get information and training of the harvesting of the fruit.	95	79.17	I
6	Cultivators should be able to get timely price information of pomegranate in various markets.	65	54.17	VII
7	Pomegranate fruits should be get the right price.	70	58.33	VI
8	Get information and guidance about foreign markets.	80	66.67	IV
9	The availability of cold storages on government basis for storage of fruits at reasonable rates.	75	62.50	V
10	The government should give impetus to start pomegranate processing industry in rural areas.	80	66.67	IV
11	Training classes should be started for making processed foods from pomegranate.	85	70.83	III

The data from the table 2 revealed that the majority (79.17%) of the pomegranate cultivators suggested get information and training of the harvesting of the fruit. 66.67 per cent suggested that information regarding proper technology of pomegranate cultivation is not yet known, Get complete knowledge about the bahar method in pomegranate suggested by (75.00%), The quantity and timing of the fertilizers to be given to the fruit cultivators should be known suggested by (70.83%) of pomegranate cultivators, Training classes should be started for making processed foods from pomegranate suggested by (70.83%) of pomegranate cultivators, The government should give impetus to start pomegranate processing industry in rural areas suggested by (66.67%) of pomegranate cultivators, Get information and guidance about foreign markets suggested by (66.67%) of pomegranate cultivators, The availability of cold storages on government basis for storage of fruits at reasonable rates suggested by (62.50%) of pomegranate cultivators, Get proper information about pest and pest management suggested by (58.33%)

of pomegranate cultivators, pomegranate fruits should be get the right price suggested by (58.33%) of pomegranate cultivators, Cultivators should be able to get timely price information of pomegranate in various markets suggested by (54.17%) of pomegranate cultivators.

Summery And Conclusion

It was found that majority of pomegranate cultivators were having constraints faced about liquid fertilizers seems expensive under the category of chemical fertilizers. Where as the context of weed management majority of pomegranate cultivators were facing the problems of lack of knowledge about usage of weedicides in scientific way and majority (79.17%) of the pomegranate cultivators suggested get information and training of the harvesting of the fruit.

References

1. **Anonymous (2018)** National Horticultural Board.
2. **Anonymous (2019)** Annual report National research on pomegranate, Solapur. 2019.